

D5.4 IMPACT CREATION AND ASSESSMENT REPORT v1

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Abstract	The deliverable gives an overview of the methodological framework of the impact assessment of the STADIEM project, as well as lists the impact measuring verticals, data gathering points and methods, responsible consortium parties as well as the impact implementation process.
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CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO	Confidential to STADIEM project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable gives an overview of the Impact Creation activities framework for the European mediatech scaling and corporate piloting project STADIEM.

Firstly, it presents the Impact assessment methodology devised during the first year of the project devised by the impact lead Storytek and validated by the consortium. It then proceeds to presenting the Minimum Viable Impact concept for impact assessment based on the “Build-Measure-Learn” principle allowing the project's impact to be mapped continuously in an experiment driven fashion, as well as delivering results to be implemented as lessons learned during the lifecycle of the project.

It also demonstrates the three verticals where STADIEM focuses its impact assessment: ecosystem, program framework and its delivery as well as communication and dissemination.

The deliverable then presents an extensive overview of impact assessment points, the frequency of the assessment, output format, as well as the responsible consortium members.

The second part of the deliverable focuses on the suggested implementation of the impact assessment. It presents the key deliverables across the project where impact results will be presented as well as the three-year implementation process for impact result analysis and publication, that will start to publicize the impact results from year two onwards based on the findings from the first cohort of Stadiem supported startups.

Report on the impact creation activities of the project, covering work done in each reporting period by all active tasks in WP5 (except T5.3) related to communication and dissemination, community building, and ecosystem building. It will also present the feedback collected for the different areas, dimensions, and types of stakeholders during impact assessment. The final report in M30 will also include lessons learned and recommendations. Any update in strategy and planned activities will also be provided as appropriate.

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INTRODUCTION

This 5.4 Impact Assessment deliverable was built on a model of AI methodology to fit the lean and agile strategy. In a timeframe going from the kickoff of the Match phase to M18, we gathered data that was then entered into the latest AI sentiment and data analytics. This provided us with time efficient, unified, and measurable data to align the answers and obtain a mappable impact.

All the other hubs from this program contributed to this deliverable: VRT, Media City Bergen (MCB), and Next Media Accelerator (NMA), but also F6S and Martel Innovate. We used reports from each hub from the Develop phase, data from the OC1 reports from F6S and overviews from the Outreach and impact creation activity report for the communication and dissemination impact section of this deliverable.

This deliverable is divided into three sections:

Firstly, we will present a report on the ecosystem impact. We will analyze the data gathered from the start-ups and corporate feedback questionnaires sent during the Integrate phase to the stakeholders that participated in the program, whether they are still in it or exited after the Match or Develop phases. We will put the key findings in perspective to the OC2, with recommendations to optimize the impact of STADIEM.

Following the ecosystem impact presentation and analysis, the second section of this deliverable will focus on the community impact. Using the same AI technology and reports from the Develop phase, we will give an overview of the community activities and achievements, based on activity trackers from each hub and corporate feedback from their collaboration with each start-up and hub. We will use this data to report on key findings and recommendations for the future cohorts of this program.

The third section of this deliverable focuses on the communication and dissemination impact: we will give an overview of the activities, goals, and objectives of Martel Innovation's work from M1 to M18 and will provide key findings and input for the OC2.

TABLE 1: TIMELINE OF THE ACTIVITIES CARRIED OUT FROM MATCH TO INTEGRATE PHASE

Date	Activity
19 May 2021	Kick-off event of Match Phase
1 July 2021	Match phase mid-term review
8-12 Nov 2021	Develop Phase mid-term review meetings
21-27 Feb 2022	Develop Phase corporate meetings
11-15 Apr 2022	Integrate Phase check-ins
07 March 2022	Questionnaire to hubs
29 March 2022	Questionnaire to start-ups
19 May 2021 - Now	Activity tracking

1. ECOSYSTEM IMPACT: START-UPS AND CORPORATES

1.1 OVERVIEW OF THE START-UPS' QUESTIONNAIRE

As part of the STADIEM Minimum Viable Impact Assessment (MVIA) strategy's second step - identify, map, and measure the outcomes of activities deployed at the Build phase – our start-ups questionnaire focuses on the Core Area 2: STADIEM framework and program deployment impact at M18. The impact is measured throughout open calls, framework deployment, program deployment, including pilots, and the impact of/on stakeholders involved in those processes. Submitted during the Integrate phase of the program – that took place between March 15th and May, 15th 2022 - to all the start-ups that entered STADIEM, this questionnaire measures the impact of the implementation of the STADIEM methodology. The data gathering measures the qualitative impact on the start-ups and analyzes the outcomes at M18. Its purpose is to analyze the financial impact of the program for the start-ups as well as to gather data about the start-ups before and during the program. We handled sentiment-oriented questions about their expectations, qualitative feedback about STADIEM and impact regarding visibility, business capacity, sustainability and viability.

1.2 RESULTS AND FINDINGS OF THE START-UPS QUESTIONNAIRE

1.2.1 OVERVIEW OF THE START-UPS AND ECOSYSTEM

The media-tech sector is still relatively young, with a big potential, and it reflects in the questionnaire: companies are growing in the area and driving the ecosystem forward, but we are at the same time analyzing a very early-stage cluster, with most companies being in their growing phase and 65.5% of them at a several paying customer stage.

Regarding the start-ups, we can acknowledge a significant diversity regarding the countries of origin of the applicants with 14 countries of registered head offices:

Out of these start-ups, 75% of the participants answering the questionnaire were CEO and Co-CEOs. As displayed below, they were employing an average of 8.6 employees.

Mapping of the number of employees per start-up

The first interesting result regarding the structure of the start-ups was the number of employees devoted to sales: considering the early stages that most of the start-ups are in, it shows a main focus on the product itself, more than scaling-up, building a viable business case or sustainability. As a consequence for STADIEM, a strong upscaling methodology can improve the impact on start-ups at earlier stages of the program.

An average of 2 employees out of ten are devoting more than 50% of their time to sales

Another key result of this start-up analysis is that the main focus of these start-ups does not seem to be investments before they enter the program: 75% had not raised any investment and if so, half of them remained under the 1M€ mark :

What has been the Investment size during STADIEM (in euros)?

The average valuation was asserted at 2.2M€. This keeps them in a fragile position before they enter STADIEM, as they fail to develop a strong strategy and timeline: in the media-tech ecosystem as well as the overall start-up ecosystem, it is a major reason for failing and these numbers are a learning point for the focus of STADIEM on this issue in the early stages of the program.

1.2.2 IMPROVEMENT OF FINANCING

Regarding the sentiment AI analysis performed on the start-ups, those that went through the three phases of the program, from Match to Integrate, when asked to rate the relevance of STADIEM in terms of branding, visibility, and promotion from 1 (bad) to 5 (excellent), gave an average of 3.8. Moreover, the clarity and effectiveness of the collaboration with STADIEM is credited with an average of 4.1. Finally, the impact on sustainability and viability receives an average of 3.7. Comparing these results with the ones who went only through the Match phase or who exited STADIEM after the Develop to Integrate evaluation is a powerful indicator of how the impact significantly grows with each phase: the satisfaction rate raises on an average of 1.5 points between the Match and the Integrate phase. The number of start-ups goes from 40 to 16 after the end of the Match phase, that lasts for 3 months, which is a very strict selection; however, this sentiment AI analysis shows the same impact at the end of the Develop phase, 6 months after, when the number goes only from 16 to 12 start-ups, indicating that the impact does not grow proportionally to the number of start-ups or the duration of the phase:

What STADIEM phases the startup/company has participated in?	How has STADIEM impacted your business capacity? Rate on a scale of 1-5 .
Match	2.384615385
Match, Develop	2.666666667
Match, Develop, Integrate	4.076923077

What STADIEM phases the startup/company has participated in?	How relevant has been the STADIEM financing towards improving your startup/company's branding, visibility or promotion? Rate on a scale of 1-5.
Match	2.307692308
Match, Develop	2.666666667
Match, Develop, Integrate	3.846153846

What STADIEM phases the startup/company has participated in?	How has STADIEM impacted your business sustainability/viability? Rate on a scale of 1-5.
Match	2.076923077
Match, Develop	3
Match, Develop, Integrate	3.692307692

Another impactful aspect of the results are the business leads credited to STADIEM: with a total of 181 with the maximum individual of 50. The program is credited to have helped mainly with business introductions and facilitation with the STADIEM logo as a visibility push.

In terms of business capacity, it was mainly credited to increased visibility: 30% of the participants to the questionnaires considered that it boosted their sales; 30 % stressed the impact in terms of clients / help with funding and regarding new features for their main product each are credited by 20% of the start-ups.

Regarding the improvement in terms of customers, it goes on an average of 75,9 to 229 during the program, from which 52 are identified as a media corporate or equivalent.

The ARR (Annual Recurring Revenue) of the start-ups, assessed at an average of 192.793€ at the start of the program is assessed at an average of 237.660€ during the participation to the program, which is a raise of 18,79%.

The start-ups, as mentioned before, are still mostly in a very young stage, and seem to focus relatively little on their investments. However, we can already observe an impact from their participation to STADIEM: their valuation, from an average of 2.2M€ before the program, raised to 2.5M€ during the program.

1.3 OVERVIEW OF CORPORATE FEEDBACK (BASED ON DEVELOP PHASE CORPORATE MEETINGS)

During the Develop phase, the 4 hubs organized corporate meetings with the start-ups and their corporate representatives under their management. We used this data to analyze their feedback on the start-ups and their collaboration for the first two phases of the program: the Match and Develop phases.

Corporate feedback was key to understand what is assessed as a good relationship with the start-ups and the hubs and how the stakeholders build a viable methodology before the Integrate phase, to optimize their products and business cases.

Overall, a weekly to bi-weekly relationship between corporate and start-up had an impact on making an agile approach work. Distant communication and difficulties to reach the corporate was a key issue for several start-ups. Corporates also asserted that start-ups that failed to integrate feedback and pivots with a weekly feedback were more likely to fail the Develop to Integrate evaluation. An agile implementation of use cases was also critical in the corporate feedback.

In general, the corporate mostly stressed pleasant, enthusiastic start-ups, open to feedback, expertise from POs and criticism. They also reported an overall very good work ethic. STADIEM registered some initial communication difficulties that mostly proved to be adapting to a new corporate timeline and departments and finding the right project owners. Workshops and meetings with experts helped the start-ups in dealing with pivots (for instance going from B2B to B2C in regard to some tools), or shifts in resources (notably to increase expenses towards cybersecurity and audits).

1.4 KEY FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

There were a few facts that came out as key findings that are to be taken into account for the second open call start-ups:

Most start-ups stressed the importance of having good quality speakers and experts along the program, to help them develop their product, but also relationship to their corporate and business cases. It was not severely impacted by COVID, since these meetings were held remotely. It shows the flexibility of the program, as the quality of the learnings delivered by these webinars, workshops and meetings was not impacted by the pivot that constituted the unexpected remoteness of activities from M1 to M18.

The impact assessment questionnaire also showed that STADIEM, despite the start-ups improvable focus on investments, helped shift this focus. It is mainly due to expert's input, however it is a key finding to implement from the earliest stages of the OC2, in order to help them present a pilotable, but also sustainable product no matter how far they make it into the program. Another key finding is the start-ups themselves: 84% of the founders are male for 16% female, whereas at employee level the repartition is of 66% male, 42% female and 2% non-binary. This lack of balance could be seen as a challenge for STADIEM to focus resources on analyzing the gender repartition at application level and how to increase the balance in the future Open Calls.

2. COMMUNITY IMPACT

2.1 FOCUS OF COMMUNITY ACTIVITIES

2.1.1 MATCH PHASE

During the Match phase, the main focus is to get to know and cooperate with the 40 start-ups and help them build a viable relationship with their corporate, identify the best PO for their product and understand the variations in timelines between a start-up and a corporate. It is a crucial phase to not only have a pilotable product but also assess a business case. The four hubs organized individual and 10-start-ups per hub meetings to allow the scale-ups to ask for specific help and to uncover their needs and expectations from the program. Main focuses include opportunity spotting, introductions to corporate, investors, experts. Since it happened during COVID, travels were not permitted to meet the hubs or to join physical events, but it focused on remote introductions that proved to be as efficient, since out of 40 start-ups, 37 came back with a letter of intent (LOI) from their corporate and some managed to secure leads.

2.1.2 DEVELOP PHASE

The main activity for the start-ups / scale-ups during the Develop Phase was to develop their solutions in co-creation with their corporate partner(s). The four hubs developed a common approach to their activities throughout the phase. They had regular meetings with each start-up throughout the phase. All four start-ups participated in individual onboarding meetings at the start of the phase, mid-term reviews, demos, and final review meetings. During the onboarding meetings the topics of discussion were their objectives in the phase, their needs, their expectations, how the hub could help, and tailoring a follow-up schedule that suited the needs and wants of the start-up. Some were more in need of coaching and to look at their progress thus far, whereas a minority favored less regular meetings and a more independent approach. At the mid-term and final review meetings, a protocol for these meetings was followed in addition to coaching on how the start-up could best prepare for the coming evaluation. In addition to these meetings, the start-ups had an open line of communication with their hubs in case of unexpected issues or needs.

2.1.3 INTEGRATE PHASE

This phase was the shortest and was also the last one under COVID restrictions, which allowed several start-ups to finally meet with their corporate and solidify their relationship with the PO and corporate hierarchy. It is a phase that is a very intense one for the start-ups, since internal testing is a moment when STADIEM has a more independent role from the relationship

between the corporate and the product. The focus was in consequence to make regular, but light follow-ups and to make the reporting process as light as possible, using a questionnaire rather than a full report. It allowed the start-ups to focus on the product, business case and to save time for their corporate.

We also implemented new tools such as Airtable as a test to use for the OC2 to gather all common data for the start-ups with various levels of access. It started a process of simplifying tools to maximize the time for the start-ups, but also to allow hubs to find all of the necessary reports, questions and calendar events and meetings at the same place. One important challenge is to have these new tools evolve and report on their impact during the OC2.

2.2 SUMMARY OF COMMUNITY ACTIVITIES AND ACHIEVEMENTS

Activities and achievements regarding the impact assessment were the following: during the match phase, most activities were online and, while being monitored and guided by the hubs, they were mostly about the start-ups setting their KPIs according to feedback and, with help from their hubs, focusing on meeting new clients, customers, leads and investors. The main goal being to get a LOI from their corporate, they had the opportunity to also focus on webinars and workshops. During the Develop phase, each hub organized a corporate meeting between the 21st and 27th February 2022. This was the last meeting before the evaluation of the start-ups to participate in the Integrate phase. It was also the only joint meeting with hubs, start-ups and corporates of this phase. It allowed each hub to compare the answers from the start-ups to the feedback from corporate regarding the framework, KPIs, overall relationship and integration of feedback and pivots. This was followed by the Integrate phase kickoff on the 15th March, 2022 and a light check-in between the 11th and 15th, April 2022. This check-in was between each hub and their start-ups to follow up on their progress in the Integration phase and check if they were on track after the corporate feedback from the end of the Develop phase.

It is stressed that the start-ups that are on track have a very agile approach and did not have major pivots during the Develop phase.

MARTEL

As Task 5.1 Leader (Outreach and impact creation strategy, plan and tools - M1-M36) Martel was in charge of communication and dissemination through STADIEM's own online outlets and communication tools (such as social media, website, newsletters, press releases), leveraging on Martel's extensive network in the ICT and EU research domain, as well as cross-posting with the accounts of partners, involved start-ups / scale-ups and similar oriented EU-funded projects and initiatives (such as Media Motor Europe and Möbius project). The external ecosystem Martel targeted and could tap on also includes: Start-up-oriented LinkedIn and Facebook groups; NGI initiative and NGI Explorer; the BDVA newsletter; 5G PPP initiative's Comm mailing list; selected contacts in the FLAME project's network and in the Fed4Fire+ project mailing list; the European Commission portal for competitive calls and calls for third parties. Dedicated one-to-one mailing - in support of Open Calls promotion - has been additionally directed to the National Contact Points (NCP) for the ICT and Future and Emerging Technologies Programs: 186 people have been contacted representing all EC Member States and Third Countries. The paid campaigns orchestrated for both Open Calls - with the direct support of VRT and F6S - resulted in a relevant impact for stakeholders' engagement, in absence of in-person promotional platforms.

2.2.1 MATCH PHASE

STADIEM's Match phase activities were impacted by covid, not in result, but in their development: As the focus of the phase being to travel in order to meet the hubs and potential leads, customers or clients did not work out, the timeline was affected as everything happened online.

The kick-off for the Match phase on May 19th 2021 was organized by NMA and MCB as a video based event with live moderation from the MCB studios. During this event the start-ups learned about the program structure, time frame and goals.

Afterwards, each hub organized individual event formats to connect the 40 start-ups with their individual corporate network. Additionally, the exchange between the start-ups and their "mother hub" was intense as there was a need for clarification and common understanding.

Due to the original plan of traveling between the hubs, the consortium developed a rotation plan for the startups. With this, no hub had to connect 40 start-ups at once with their network but could organize meetings and calls on demand.

The Match phase lasted for two months with a mid-term review after four weeks.

Nearly all start-ups managed to achieve a relevant LOI which shows that the organization of this phase was quite successful given the circumstances and necessary changes due to the pandemic.

2.2.2 DEVELOP PHASE

The Develop Phase was kicked off with an onboarding meeting where all 16 selected start-ups/scale-ups were invited to get a briefing of expected outcomes, processes, and deadlines during the Develop Phase. The start-ups/scale-ups were then divided between the innovation hubs, where each was responsible for 4 start-ups/scale-ups best suited to the hubs' expertise. The mother hubs assisted with coaching, follow-up, and served as the main point of contact for each start-up/scale-up throughout the entirety of the Phase.

Halfway through the Phase the consortium organized a mid-term review of the start-ups / scale-ups progress and results consisting of mid-term review meetings with the hubs, submission of a mid-term report, and a mid-term Investment Committee Meeting. In the final weeks of the Phase is the final evaluation period. Here, each start-up / scale-up meets with their mother hub for a final review meeting, they have a demo for the corporate and mother hub, the hubs meet with the corporate to get their insights, and finally on 2 March 2022, the final Investment Committee Meeting took place, where the 12 top-performing start-ups/scale-ups were selected to proceed to the Integrate Phase.

Throughout the Develop Phase, there were organized monthly upskilling sessions called Training Tuesdays, and monthly social events called Humans of STADIEM. In addition to this, the consortium organized several networking and showcasing events. The start-ups/scale-ups were invited to pitch and network at Future Week in Bergen, to exhibit at IBC in Amsterdam, to pitch at MCB Expo, and to have a Demo Day at the end of the phase. Due to Covid-19 restrictions, IBC and the Demo Day were canceled.

During the Develop Phase the mother hub assisted with coaching, follow-up, and served as the main point of contact for the start-up/scale-up. The mother hubs provided their start-ups with individual check-ins and follow up meetings based on the individual needs and wants of the start-up/scale-up. These meetings were additional to the mother hub and start-up/scale-up meetings part of the evaluation and selection process. In addition to the check-ins, the mother hubs also facilitated business and investor introductions with companies in their networks based on the needs for each start-up/scale-up.

The hubs had on average 5 to 10 check-ins and follow-up meetings with each of the 4 beneficiaries. Besides general inquiries about the status (mostly lasting one hour), this follow-up could also entail, depending on the need and the solution of the start-up, the facilitation of workshops between the beneficiary and the corporate in order to make expectations and needs towards the solution clear: for instance, setting-up of technical or small user tests or mediation between corporate and beneficiary.

2.2.3 INTEGRATE PHASE

The Integrate Phase, although only lasting two months, took over the main organizational principles from the Develop Phase in regard to community activities. Here as well, a general approach over the hubs was implemented. On the one hand there was the more formal program of mid-term review, final check-in and investment committee, on the other hand the hubs also provided individual support via checks-in and follow-up meetings especially in the beginning of the Integrate Phase. Due to the short period and the timing of the mid-term review and the investment committee meeting, much of this follow-up activities are rather hands-on and very specific in nature compared to the more regularly planned and broader focus of the check-ins in the previous phase.

In the case of the VRT motherhub specific 2-hour kick-off meetings were organized from 14th March onwards between the corporate and the beneficiary in order to align on the objectives of the phase and the results that needed to be obtained, as well on the timing of operations and needs to make the phase successful. Such a clear view and agreement supports the realization of the key-KPI's proposed in the integration phase plan. Afterwards more punctual support was provided based on the needs of the beneficiary.

The four hubs had a common approach. They had several meetings with each start-up throughout the phase, with all participating in an individual onboarding meeting and mid-term review meeting. During the onboarding meetings the topics of discussion were their objectives in the phase, their needs, their expectations, their communication and integration of corporate feedback and tailoring of a follow-up schedule that suited the needs and wants of the start-up. The hubs then had to adapt to various approaches from the start-ups such as meeting frequency or tools of communication - Slack, emails, phone or Google meet.

2.3 SUMMARY AND ANALYSIS OF THE ACTIVITY TRACKER

The activity tracker during the Match and Develop phases was developed to gather data on each meeting between the start-ups and their hubs, as well as corporate meetings and overall

exchanges between the different stakeholders. It allowed the hubs to follow up on corporate recommendations and availability towards the start-ups

During the Match and Develop phases, the meetings (check-ins, follow-up, mid-term reviews, demos, final reviews and other meetings) were recorded for each of the beneficiaries in an activity tracker document. A record contained the date, the duration of the activity, the persons involved (on the corporate level, on the beneficiary level and on the VRT Stadiem team level) in the meeting and a short summary of the various points discussed or remarks made. In that way it was possible for the hubs to see if a previously mentioned issue or recommendation by the corporate was not solved or, more positively, where this feedback from the corporate had been fruitfully taken into consideration. It also allowed hubs to follow up on each other's activities and prepare better for Investment Committee meetings and evaluations.

MARTEL

Martel's record of online activities could leverage on both social media and website analytics, showing a total estimated reach of 1,000,000 stakeholders throughout all communication channels combined (10k in terms of website visitors alone). Martel could also draw an overview of events' reach based on information gathered by the partners, and analysis of registrations for the Open Call's info webinars, for an estimated reach of over 40,000 stakeholders. More details can be found in D5.8 (Outreach and impact creation report v1).

2.4 KEY FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The hubs had a very common approach regarding the start-ups activities and tracking, which made it easier when 2 of them exited the program thanks to exciting deals and the repartition of the start-ups was readjusted. A regular and close check-in of the activities and one-on-one meetings with each start-up made it easier for them to ask more specific questions that could not be possible in a group meeting or in a short check-in. It proved very important to have experts as early as possible in the phase, as well as webinars and regular external expertise to teach the start-ups efficient tools to build an efficient and clear relationship with their corporate, develop clear and manageable KPIs and understand how to integrate and pilot their product and develop necessary features. Several start-ups struggled to understand where to focus their resources in order to be on various fronts at the same time and therefore needed guidance from former successful exit founders on early-stage sustainability building.

Also, the relationship between the hubs and the start-up is crucial for the program's efficiency, as each hub brings a different input to the consortium, as they are from different countries, different sizes and different structures; in order to help the start-ups in their lean strategy, time efficiency and unified guidance from each hub is needed.

Now that traveling is possible again, a challenge is to solidify the relationship between the hubs by meeting in person and learn more about each other. It is important that the members of the consortium know as much as possible of the ecosystem to offer consistent and efficient work.

3. ECOSYSTEM IMPACT: START-UPS AND CORPORATES

3.1 FOCUS ON COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES, GOALS AND OBJECTIVES

STADIEM addresses three key points in the European media sector (a) cross border scalability, (b) startup to corporate to market tech transfer and (c) availability of innovative media services in a Digital Single Market framework. As such STADIEM's ambition is to contribute to identifying, nurturing, and retaining promising start-ups and connecting them with media industries by creating concrete opportunities to collaborate.

Outreach and impact creation activities are central to the overall STADIEM goal. They are being closely monitored and coordinated to ensure a broad visibility and an effective engagement of all targeted stakeholders in the Next Generation Media, including those from the media and non-media sectors (verticals). These activities are coordinated by Martel with active contributions from all STADIEM partners, following the following objectives:

- Ensure STADIEM's broad visibility by spreading knowledge about the project and its results, as well as establishing a distinctive and recognizable identity that will support promotional and marketing efforts.
- Reach a wide network of innovators interested in taking part in the STADIEM Open Calls (2).
- Reach, stimulate and engage a critical mass of relevant stakeholders to ensure that (a) the Open Calls and Incubation program of the project are effectively and properly disseminated to the targeted audiences for maximum participation and promotion, (b) the results of the project and 3rd party projects, selected through STADIEM Open Calls, are effectively showcased, leading to validation, improvement and possibly further adoption of the developed technologies and concepts.
- Facilitate exploitation of the project's outcomes and promote the development of innovative solutions based on the STADIEM technologies and concepts.
- To fully support the key players' engagement strategy in the project activities and concepts around the Open Calls and the Incubation program, while promoting and providing great visibility on the 3rd party projects and the best practices learned that will lead to the creation of a new business model in the media domain.
- Establish strong liaisons and ensure close collaboration with relevant initiatives in the media industry.

3.2 SUMMARY OF COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

As mentioned in the Deliverable 5.8 about the Outreach and Impact Creation, outreach and impact creation activities are central to the overall STADIEM goal. They are being closely monitored and coordinated to ensure a broad visibility and an effective engagement of all targeted stakeholders in the Next Generation Media, including those from the media and non-media sectors (verticals). These activities are coordinated by Martel with active contributions from all STADIEM partners, following the following objectives:

3.2.1 WEBSITE

Launched at the beginning of the project (M2), the STADIEM website (<https://www.stadiem.eu>) has been developed to act as an information hub presenting the project’s goals, activities, and achievements. To this purpose, contents have been constantly updated.

The website is being periodically updated according to the progress of the project. Until today (end of March 2022), the website counts around 10,400 unique visitors, who generated around **22,900 page views** on an **average visit duration of 01’17”**.

The figures below provide the aforementioned plus some additional details: Figure 1 (Traffic overview and visit duration), Figure 2 (Top visited pages) and Figure 3 (Visits per country).

FIGURE 1: STADIEM WEBSITE - TRAFFIC OVERVIEW AND VISIT DURATION

Page	Page Views	Unique Page Views	Avg. Time on Page	Entrances	Bounce Rate	% Exit
1. /open-call-2/	4,223 (16.94%)	3,788 (18.21%)	00:03:47	3,268 (21.08%)	85.74%	81.93%
2. /	2,332 (9.36%)	1,997 (9.60%)	00:01:12	1,831 (11.81%)	37.74%	38.25%
3. /open-call-1/	1,470 (5.90%)	1,316 (6.33%)	00:02:31	954 (6.15%)	78.20%	72.11%
4. /about/	493 (1.98%)	427 (2.05%)	00:01:42	145 (0.94%)	48.97%	36.71%
5. /faqs/	484 (1.94%)	411 (1.98%)	00:03:53	178 (1.15%)	75.28%	61.16%
6. /open-calls/	470 (1.89%)	402 (1.93%)	00:01:30	175 (1.13%)	53.71%	37.87%
7. /consortium/	345 (1.38%)	320 (1.54%)	00:01:20	81 (0.52%)	62.96%	38.26%
8. /how-stadium-works/	258 (1.04%)	236 (1.13%)	00:01:47	59 (0.38%)	62.71%	37.21%
9. /news/	253 (1.02%)	216 (1.04%)	00:00:39	48 (0.31%)	45.83%	26.88%
10. /scaleups/	243 (0.97%)	201 (0.97%)	00:00:46	60 (0.39%)	20.00%	14.81%

FIGURE 2: STADIEM WEBSITE – TOP VISITED PAGES

Country	Users	% Users
1. Romania	1,025	9.83%
2. Bulgaria	696	6.67%
3. Cyprus	683	6.55%
4. Belgium	662	6.35%
5. Greece	592	5.68%
6. Germany	572	5.48%
7. Croatia	336	3.22%
8. United Kingdom	328	3.15%
9. Poland	302	2.90%
10. Portugal	295	2.83%

FIGURE 3: STADIEM WEBSITE – VISITS PER COUNTRY

All information and e-mails collected are protected under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

3.2.2 SOCIAL MEDIA

STADIEM established its presence on social media channels to regularly promote the project activities and outputs while encouraging a wider promotion of Next Generation Media solutions. The project has built a fair follower base on several social media channels, namely Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube, which are all linked to the project's website.

1. Twitter

STADIEM uses Twitter as a social network to cover the news in real-time, cross-share relevant and interesting initiatives, and to establish meaningful connections with relevant stakeholders, including policy makers, industry, and the general public. So far, the [STADIEM Twitter account](#) has **reached 208 followers** (including project partners, similar projects, interested stakeholders, etc.). In total, around 367 tweets have been posted. The project also follows 86 accounts, mostly projects and initiatives in similar fields or of approximate nature where partners have been involved. Over the duration of Open Call 2's promotion, the average engagement rate was 3,8% (with peaks reaching 23%) and the account registered over 19,000 total clicks.

2. LinkedIn

LinkedIn allows the project to network with individuals and organizations within the media industry and beyond, share relevant information about project activities, and stay up to date on the latest developments in the field. [The LinkedIn account](#) has gathered **429 followers** so far. Similarly to Twitter, the LinkedIn account is mostly used to share the latest progress of STADIEM, echoing key promotional messages from the project website and sharing relevant news from the project's partners, relevant projects and the European Commission. During the recent Open Call 2 promotion, the account reached a peak of 418 unique visitors, in an audience prevalently working in the fields of business development, entrepreneurship and media and communications.

3. YouTube

STADIEM has also created an [account on YouTube](#), one of the leading video-sharing platforms. This channel has been opened at the early project stages to disseminate the first project video. Since then, the project has released a total of **22 videos** on the channel. For more details on the channel's reach and content, please refer to section 2.3.1.

3.2.3 NEWSLETTERS, VIDEO & PRESS RELEASES

The STADIEM consortium keeps the community and the general public informed about relevant activities, undertakings, and events by regularly publishing news items and press releases. To date, **19 news items** have been published on the project website.

5 Newsletters - collecting such items, plus additional strategic communication - have been edited and distributed to stakeholders through STADIEM's mailing lists as well as made available on the project website. According to the outreach plan, the initial goal would have been to have 6 newsletters by M18, but a decision was taken to delay the 1st newsletter, to have it coincide with the launch of OC1; therefore, an additional newsletter/newsflash will be released in the second half of the project. So far, **281 stakeholders have subscribed** to receive STADIEM's Newsletters. In terms of further analysis on the efficiency of the communication:

- The 1st newsletter (February 2021) was sent to 58 subscribers / 87% opens / 24% clicks
- The 2nd newsletter (May 2021) was sent to 224 subscribers / 58% opens / 21% clicks
- The 3rd newsletter (September 2021) was sent out to 246 subscribers / 55% opens / 15% clicks
- The 4th newsletter (December 2021) was sent out to 265 subscribers / 58% opens / 17% clicks
- The 5th newsletter (February 2022) was sent out to 276 subscribers / 54% opens / 12% clicks

In the first reporting period STADIEM released **22 videos** which have been uploaded on the STADIEM YouTube channel and mirrored on STADIEM's website. So far, the project's YouTube Channel has reached a total of **1,879 views**. Although some of the videos were specifically conceived to support the Open Calls (both in terms of advertising and guidance for potential applicants), most of the videos also allowed to promote the project's incubation and acceleration program.

To date, **6 press releases** have been issued by STADIEM, matching with key moments such as the launch of both Open Calls and announcements related to the selection phases of the project's piloting and acceleration program. All press releases were made available on the [dedicated section of the project's website](#). The 4th and 5th press releases (issued in September and December 2021) were also respectively **distributed to 30 and 150 contacts in the specialized press** through [Prowly](#); the 5th press release being specifically designed to promote the launch of the Open Call 2.

3.2.4 WORKSHOPS AND WEBINARS

In line with what anticipated in Section 4.3 of D5.2, **STADIEM organized 4 info webinars** presenting to launch and present the Open Calls. The webinars were promoted across the stakeholders identified under Task 1.1 (Community Building Strategy and community management) through the online communication channels, and with the support of 2 advertising campaigns (see section 2.6). The scope of the webinars was to inform innovative start-ups/scale-ups of the objectives and conditions of participation to the STADIEM Open Calls.

The two **OC1 webinars** (held on 22nd February and 10th March 2021) reached **90 and 70 participants**, while the two **OC2 webinars** (held on 28th January and 10th February 2022) reached **45 and 36 participants**. As detailed in Section 2.3.1, all webinars were recorded and made available through STADIEM's YouTube channel and website (both in the OCs info pages and in the "Videos" section) – The release of the recordings was also promoted via social media.

4. CONCLUSION

This deliverable presents the impact assessment methodology for Stadiem as an ambitious business scaling project for the mediatech startups and was discussed by the consortium members at a General Assembly, and implemented in full capacity during the second year of the project. However, the impact assessment is relying on activities that go from the Match phase to the Integrate phase, so from the first year of the programme to an on-going phase.

The data points that are described here are varied: community mapping, startup performances and feedback from hubs and corporates, hub activities overview and analysis, overall consortium performance overview – gathered from the beginning of the project, dissemination feedback – also gathered continuously - and give an overview of the ecosystem at various time points and show the unified way STADIEM's role in this ecosystem to scale-up companies.

This deliverable also breaks down this impact assessment by analyzing the various activities according to the phase the program is in and how exponential the impact is. It is a central starting point to understand how each phase entails specific guidance, needs and expectations from the start-ups, and how to target specific issues when inviting experts and organize workshops and webinars to fit each phase's needs.

The hub's activities are described as unified and agreed upon during consortium meetings and debated over. They are aligned to fit the lean strategy described in the Impact Assessment and to give comparable and similar data over the program.

The data points combined give us a very clear picture of the European scale-up landscape and gives us central axes to focus on to improve the ecosystem and learn from the OC1 for the OC2.

ANNEX I : LIST OF TABLES

Stage	Impact Action	Output	Frequency	Collection Form	KPI
Ecosystem Impact	Impact to Mediatech community	Stadium community & Ecosystem Map	Twice per project	Community Map in the project's repository at Google Drive, deliverables D1.6 and D.1.7	Twice per project
	Impact to external stakeholders	Engagement calendar & log	Continuous	Engagement Calendar at Airtable	10 networking meetings per hub and stakeholders per stage
	Impact to Startup Community	Engagement calendar & log	Continuous	Engagement Calendar at Airtable	10 networking meetings per hub and stakeholders per stage
	Impact to investors/portfolio managers	Investor / Portfolio Manager Study	Once per cohort	Google Forms by the projects repository project's repository at Google Drive	
	Impact assessment from Advisory Board	Feedback to consortium	At least twice per project	Advisory board notes in project's repository at Google Drive	
	Impact to Local Ecosystems	Local Ecosystem reports	Once per Cohort	Engagement Calendar at Airtable	10 networking meetings per hub and stakeholders per stage
Framework & Program Deployment Impact	Impact to Hubs: Implementation of the Stadium methodology	Stadium Framework & Activity Calendar	Continuous	Activity Calendar & Log at Airtable	

	Qualitative Impact to the Hubs	Workshop	Twice per project	Workshop outcomes, Deliverables 2.3 and D2.4 and final report	
	Qualitative feedback from the Startups	Stage Report of Beneficiaries (from Match onwards)	Once per Stage	Stage questionnaire as part of stage performance evaluation	
	Maturation of innovative technologies & business processes	TRL Assessment post cohort	Once per cohort	Cohort assessment report as part of project management deliverables	
	Impact to improved cross border business activities	Cross border networking + pilot report	Once per cohort	Cohort assessment questionnaire at Airtable	
	Pilot quality	Corporate assessment survey	Once per cohort	Corporate assessment questionnaire at Airtable	
	Impact to Open Calls	Open call report	Once per cohort	Open call deliverables	
Communication & Dissemination Impact	Media Dissemination Impact	Dissemination report	Once per reporting period	Dissemination report at notes in project's repository at Google Drive, D5.8, D5.9	D5.8 delivered at M18
	Website impact	Dissemination report	Once per reporting period	Dissemination report at notes in project's repository at Google Drive	>10k since inception
	Publication Impact	Dissemination report	Once per reporting period	Dissemination report at notes in project's repository at Google Drive	6 publications in news outlets
	Social Media Impact	Dissemination report		Dissemination report at notes in project's repository at Google Drive	208 Followers Twitter 429 Followers LinkedIn >1M impressions altogether

	Presentation Impact	Events Report	Once per reporting period	Dissemination report at notes in project's repository at Google Drive	9 Presentations; estimated reach >12k stakeholders
	Event Impact	Events Report	Once per reporting period	Dissemination report at notes in project's repository at Google Drive	33 Events attended; estimated reach 40k stakeholders

Table 1. Stadiem project impact assessment breakdown

The following table (Table 2) describes the responsibilities of impact data gathering throughout the consortium.

Stage	Impact Action	Output	Collection Form	Main Responsible
Ecosystem Impact	Impact to Mediatech community	Stadiem community & Ecosystem Map	Community Map in the project's repository at Google Drive	VRT
	Impact to external stakeholders	Engagement calendar & log	Engagement Calendar at Airtable	All partners
	Impact to Startup Community	Engagement calendar & log	Engagement Calendar at Airtable	All partners
	Impact to investors/portfolio managers	Investor / Portfolio Manager Study	Google Forms by the projects repository project's repository at Google Drive	Storytek / Exit Academy
	Impact assessment from Advisory Board	Feedback to consortium	Advisory board notes in project's repository at Google Drive	NMA
	Impact to Local Ecosystems	Local Ecosystem reports	Engagement Calendar at Airtable	All partners
Framework & Program	Impact to Hubs: Implementation of	Stadiem Framework &	Activity Calendar & Log at Airtable	All partners

Deployment Impact	the Stadiem methodology	Activity Calendar		
	Qualitative Impact to the Hubs	Workshop	Workshop outcomes, Deliverable 1.3 and final report	Storytek
	Qualitative feedback from the Startups	Stage Report of Beneficiaries (from Match onwards)	Stage questionnaire as part of stage performance evaluation	Stage responsible partners, NMA, VRT, Storytek, MCB
	Maturation of innovative technologies & business processes	TRL Assessment post cohort	Cohort assessment report as part of project management deliverables	VRT
	Impact to improved cross border business activities	Cross border networking + pilot report	Cohort assessment questionnaire at Airtable	Storytek, VRT
	Pilot quality	Corporate assessment survey	Corporate assessment questionnaire at Airtable	Storytek, VRT
	Impact to Open Calls	Open call report	Open call deliverables	F6S
Communication & Dissemination Impact	Media Dissemination Impact	Dissemination report	Dissemination report at notes in project's repository at Google Drive	Martel Innovate
	Website impact	Dissemination report	Dissemination report at notes in project's repository at Google Drive	Martel Innovate
	Publication Impact	Dissemination report	Dissemination report at notes in project's repository at Google Drive	Martel Innovate
	Social Media Impact	Dissemination report	Dissemination report at notes in project's repository at Google Drive	Martel Innovate
	Presentation Impact	Events Report	Dissemination report at notes in project's repository at Google Drive	Martel Innovate
	Event Impact	Events Report	Dissemination report at notes in project's	Martel Innovate

			repository at Google Drive	
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Table 2. Stadiem project impact assessment responsibilites allocation